

Lessons recordings and related materials

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The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union, neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
FBP	Fish by-products
FBGC	Food and Bio Cluster Denmark
FCP	Fish co-products
UNIPA	University of Palermo
EMU	EESTI MAULIKOOL, Estonian University of Life Science
UiA	University of Agder
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea

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1. Aim of the deliverable

This deliverable is associated with the lessons recording and related training materials, developed by pilot case studies within the BlueRev Project, as part of the actions aimed to revitalise European local communities in the blue bio-based sector.

The BlueRev Project, in fact, was focussed on promoting the sustainable transformation of the blue economy through innovation, knowledge sharing and capacity building in marine resource management.

The partners involved in this action implemented an extensive training programme comprising four thematic modules and a total of 24 lessons, to share principles, methodologies, protocols, scientific results and technological innovations with a diverse audience, including academics, industry professionals and policymakers.

Each training session addressed key topics such as monitoring marine ecosystems, sustainable fisheries, the circular economy, and technologies for mitigating pollution. To maximise accessibility and impact, all sessions were recorded and supplemented with a range of learning resources, including presentation slides, reading materials and interactive tools. This collection of recordings and related materials has been organised to ensure long-term accessibility for stakeholders in the research, industry and policy sectors.

One of the main focuses of the trainings was to promote the blue careers within the framework of a sustainable Blue Economy, with the goal of fostering the next generation of blue skills and creating opportunities for appealing and enduring sustainable maritime professions. Their contribution, through participation in training activities, provision of field-based insights and dissemination of content at a local level, helped to tailor the materials to real-world challenges and amplify the programme's impact.

These materials, available for the end-users, include:

- **training materials**, such as slides, supplementary readings and interactive resources;
- **recorded webinars**, available as open-access video and audio files;
- **online repository** (hosted on the project website, which allows stakeholders to freely access and download all content).

The training programme was included in the project to give a significant contribution to the achievement of BlueRev's objectives by facilitating knowledge transfer, stakeholder engagement and capacity building across the European blue economy landscape. Participants' feedback emphasized the relevance and clarity of the sessions, and there was strong interest in including additional case studies and interactive elements in future training initiatives.

This report aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the BlueRev training program, starting from the rationale to the structure description, such as recorded lessons and related materials produced during the project, with the objective to:

- provide a clear understanding of the scope and structure of the training content;
- detail the contents of each module and lesson, as well as the accessibility of the materials to all stakeholders.
- ensure that key stakeholders, including researchers, master and PhD students, industry professionals, and policymakers, have access to valuable knowledge resources generated through the project.

By doing so, the training programme supports the broader objective of fostering a sustainable, innovation-driven blue economy across Europe.

Additionally, the report highlights how the materials are disseminated through the project's public website to ensure broad accessibility and engagement.

This deliverable is not only a record of the project's educational activities but would like to also be a valuable resource for future activities.

By preserving the training content and ensuring open access to it, this deliverable will serve as a long-term support tool for capacity building, skill development, and policy innovation in the blue economy sector. This allows the knowledge generated to be continuously used and adapted, thereby extending the impact of the BlueRev project beyond its formal duration.

This ensures that the BlueRev project's outcomes meaningfully contribute to advancing the blue economy community.

2. Introduction

2.1. Conceptual framework

This deliverable could be intended as a reference handbook useful to develop training on Blue Economy in specific European Regions; the development and coordination of the training program was in charge of the University of Palermo (UNIPA), as leader of Task 5.2, in close cooperation with key project partners involved in the training, such as Food and Bio Cluster Denmark (FBGC), the Estonian University of Life Sciences (EMU), the coordinator, Agency for the Promotion of European Research (APRE), and other consortium members. This collaborative framework ensured the integration of diverse expertise and perspectives, resulting in the creation of training materials tailored to the needs of a wide range of stakeholders.

According to the EU Blue Economy Report, released by the European Commission (2024), the term Blue Economy includes economic activities that are:

- (a) **marine-based**, including capture fisheries and aquaculture, offshore oil and gas, offshore wind energy, ocean energy, desalination, shipping and maritime transport, and marine and coastal tourism;
- (b) **marine-related** activities which use products and/or produce products and services for the ocean and marine-based activities; for example, seafood processing, marine biotechnology, shipbuilding and repair, port activities, maritime communication, maritime equipment, maritime insurance and maritime surveillance.

The marine living resources sector covers the primary sector (harvesting of renewable biological resources), their processing (conversion into food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy), and distribution along the supply chain. Within this sector, the Blue biotechnology considers the unconventional or under-exploited groups of marine organisms and their biomass applications, and it was just in this direction that the project BlueRev focused on, also to incentivize new job opportunities in the blue biotech sector.

The processing sector employed about 211300 persons, accounting for 39% of jobs, while primary production (fishery and aquaculture) employed slightly more than 200200 persons (37%) and processing of fish products about 131500 persons (24%) (EU, 2024), thus there is the need to improve recruitment of new generations, skilled in the blue sector (Figure 1).

Employment by Member State

Figure 1: Share of employment in EU Marine living resources sector, 2021

(Adapted from the EU Blue bioeconomy report, 2024)

The Blue Economy also includes those parts of the public sector with direct coastal and ocean responsibilities, as well as marine education and research and blue biotechnology.

The EU Blue Economy is estimated to grow in the upcoming years, driven by the transition to a sustainable and circular economy, the ambitious net zero climate targets, and a focus on innovation and research. To approach this growth, new curricula must be created to guarantee the achievement of professional skills in the different areas of the Blue Growth.

Consumers become more conscious of environmental sustainability and of the impact of their choices on natural resources, particularly Marine living resources, Maritime transport, port activities and energy sources.

The economic outlook will show variations across different Blue Economy sectors, depending on their diverse specificities, such as maturity, resource availability, and global competitiveness.

The socio-economic performance of the Blue Economy sectors will also depend on their different reaction to climate change, which can have detrimental effects on fisheries, aquaculture, and marine biodiversity, ultimately affecting the economic viability of these sectors. Overfishing and unsustainable fishing practices continue to pose a threat to marine resources, potentially leading to stock depletion and ecosystem damage

Addressing these challenges will be crucial to maintaining a positive trajectory and ensuring the sustainability transition of the EU Blue Economy in the coming years.

The ongoing transition is attracting investments in the development and scaling up of new technologies for the growth of the Blue Economy. This will be accompanied by the creation of new jobs and economic opportunities.

Our coasts and seas have the potential to deliver sustainable growth and jobs in the coming years and contribute towards the Green Deal objectives. This will only be possible if we invest in new, blue skills and career development.

A competitive, resilient and socially fair blue economy needs highly qualified and skilled professionals. Today, many blue economy sectors have difficulties finding the right people with adequate competencies, which hampers their growth.

The European Commission is supporting actions to solve this problem by supporting specific training actions for the blue economy that can:

- reduce the skills gap between the education system and the needs of the labour market;
- improve communication and cooperation between the education sector and the productive sector;
- improve the attractiveness and awareness of career opportunities in the blue economy.

Demand is increasing for programs in ocean sciences that address workforce development and leadership training needs to support both the traditional and emerging new blue economy.

University degrees and undergraduate programs that provide marine-related technical training represent an opportunity for growth in the blue economy that combine management and marine science training for students interested in developing skills applicable to the new blue economy. Furthermore, the development of new instructional programs provides an opportunity to strengthen collaboration between industry, public institutions and academia in building a new workforce that meets the needs of the blue economy (Bradley Moran, 2021). Furthermore, the EU commission incentivizes specific training also within HORIZON Europe projects, like BlueRev, as strategy to support curricula creations at region level, that, starting from local needs, could turn professionalization into new opportunities in the blue economy (Boriello et al. 2024).

To support the objectives of the updated European Bioeconomy Strategy and the EU Green Deal, the BlueRev project proposes the concept described in Figure 2.

Figure 2: BlueRev project concept

The overall concept of the BlueRev project is based on the revitalisation of European local communities with innovative bio-based business, governance models and social innovations focused on the blue bio-based sector, by demonstrating the benefits the wide deployment of the bio-based economy can offer. The project takes into account three model regions, the Northern, Southern and Central-Eastern Europe (Figure 3), giving a sound geographical balance to the project and covering almost all blue bio-based productive sectors including algae, fisheries and aquaculture. In this way the results can be replicated throughout Europe in other regions showing similar assets and conditions, under a fully transferable case-study approach.

Region	Value chain	Description
 Marine bioactive compounds and ingredients from fish processing residuals and algae for industrial applications.	The main bottlenecks are represented by the lack of infrastructure and governance measures/business models for the collection, stocking, and selling of marine by-products. A gap in the connection between production and end-users (e.g., companies in the sector of cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and pharmaceuticals).	
 Use of fish side-streams for nutraceutical, food and feed applications.	The uptake of blue bio-based economy value chains faces problems related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of skilled personnel • logistic infrastructures • being an outermost region (Greenland). 	

Figure 3: Model regions in BlueRev

In order to increase opportunities to develop skilled jobs and small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy, thus helping to revitalise local communities and to increase opportunities created by the local bio-based economy within the broader bioeconomy transition, BlueRev performed a plan of training events for around 500 participants, according to input/feedback collected during the workshops in WP3 and WP4. Lessons were recorded and all materials are made available to the stakeholders through the project's public website.

3. The Training Programme

The training programme is represented by the following components:

- this document;
- the BlueRev training contents, accessible by login into the BlueRev platform, at the following link: <https://support-tool.BlueRevproject.eu/>, which includes:
 - PowerPoint presentation for each lecturer (topic);
 - recorded webinars related to each PowerPoint.

The programme was structured around four core modules, comprising a total of 24 lessons, coordinated by the three project partners involved.

These modules were developed to address key areas of marine resource management, sustainable practices, and innovative approaches fostered by the project. The primary objective of the training programme is to facilitate knowledge transfer and promote cross-sectoral collaboration among stakeholders from academia, industry, and policy-making institutions.

The programme was designed with the following objectives:

- to provide a holistic approach to marine ecosystem management, sustainability, and policy development;
- to ensure broad stakeholder engagement from various sectors of the blue economy;
- to deliver high-quality, accessible training resources that contribute to the long-term capacity-building goals of the BlueRev project.

4. UNIPA Training

The training programme developed and coordinated by UNIPA has been specifically designed to provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of both theoretical principles and practical methodologies related to the extraction of marine bioactive compounds from fish by-products (FBP) and fish co-products (FCP). The programme aims to promote circular economy practices within the marine biotechnology sector, thereby supporting sustainable development and innovation in line with the European Green Deal and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The course highlights the intrinsic link between circularity and sustainability, beginning with the sustainable exploitation of aquatic resources and the valorisation of by-products, and emphasizing their strategic importance for the development of the local blue economy. Particular attention was given to the potential applications of marine bioactive compounds in the production of high-value ingredients for the food, feed, pharmaceutical, and cosmeceutical sectors, thereby promoting sustainable blue growth.

4.1. Structure of the Programme

The training was divided into two modules, each of which was tailored to the needs of a specific target audience (SMEs or master's and PhD students). The modules were designed to ensure both knowledge transfer and practical application.

4.2. Module 1: Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy

This module was specifically designed for SMEs in the seafood sector, producer associations, fishermen/fish processors, and new investors interested in entering the blue biotechnology field.

The training aimed to strengthen the capacity of small-scale actors to engage with circular value chains through the valorisation of marine biomass residues.

Link to the repository: [Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy](#)

Topic 1: Best practices for the characterisation and selection of fish by-products (FBP) and fish co-products (FCP) from fisheries, aquaculture and processing plants, to be applied at an industrial level

This module includes the description of the valorization of by-products originated from the most important local value chains: fishery, aquaculture and fish processing.

Key contents:

The module includes three dedicated lessons to explore:

- Criteria for identifying high-value by-products suitable for biotechnological applications;
- Methods for initial sorting and quality assessment of FBPs and FCPs at source;
- Case studies showcasing successful valorisation pathways implemented by SMEs and cooperatives.

The training bridges the gap between primary producers and downstream industries by facilitating the integration of small-scale stakeholders into circular bio-based value chains and promoting the sustainable exploitation of marine biomass resources.

4.3. Module 2: Training and coaching programme to increase skilled job opportunities

The second module was designed to support Master and PhD students, including those from the FORTHEM Alliance, in developing advanced skills for sustainable innovation and entrepreneurship in the blue bioeconomy.

The module was organised into two main thematic areas (topic 1 and topic 2), combining specialised knowledge transfer with coaching activities to support the development of blue career profiles. It aimed to equip participants with advanced theoretical and practical skills relevant to marine biotechnology, industrial innovation, and circular economy applications, fostering both entrepreneurial and research-oriented professional pathways in the blue bioeconomy sector.

By promoting an interdisciplinary and practice-oriented approach, the training empowers participants to apply theoretical concepts to real-world challenges, thus supporting career development in both research-driven and entrepreneurial contexts.

Link to the repository: [Training and coaching programme to increase skilled job opportunities](#)

Topic 1: Methods for the extraction of bioactive compounds from fish by-products (FBP) and fish co-products (FCP) from pilot to industrial scale

This topic focused on the advanced methodologies for extracting bioactive compounds from fish by-products (FBP) and fish co-products (FCP). Emphasis was placed on the transition from laboratory-scale processes to pilot and industrial applications, highlighting the challenges and opportunities associated with scaling up.

Link to the repository: [Methods for extraction of bioactive compounds from fish by product and fish co products from pilot to industrial scale](#)

Key contents:

- Comparative analysis of traditional versus green extraction techniques, with attention to sustainability and compound integrity;
- Recovery of target bioactives, including proteins, peptides, omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), carotenoids, and polyphenols;
- Introduction to technological innovations, including supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) and eco-friendly alternatives suitable for industrial integration.

Topic 2: Valorisation of bioactive compounds from FBP and FCP in cosmetics, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals

The second topic focused on the valorisation of extracted marine bioactives in cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and pharmaceutical sectors identified as strategically important for the future of the blue bioeconomy.

Link to the repository: [Valorisation of bioactive compounds from FBP and FCP in cosmetics, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals](#)

Key contents:

- Nutraceutical and pharmaceutical applications of enriched fish oils, with particular focus on omega-3 fatty acids and their health-promoting properties.
- Cosmeceutical potential of marine-derived polyphenols, emphasising their role in anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant formulations.
- Valorization of carotenoids (e.g, astaxanthin) from crustacean by-products, highlighting their use in functional foods, dietary supplements, animal feed, and human health applications. Successful case studies and business models demonstrating the commercialisation of marine bioactives;
- Innovation strategies for positioning these compounds in competitive and regulated markets;
- Examples of value chain integration, connecting extraction technologies with final product development in the blue bioeconomy.

Webinar associated with the training

Link to the repository:

- [Methods for extraction of bioactive compounds from fish by product and fish co products from pilot to industrial scale](#)
- [From conventional methods to green technologies and comparison of yield, quality and bioactivities of the fraction/compounds extracted](#)
- [Extraction of fish oils and enrichment in omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids \(PUFA\)](#)
- [Evaluation of bioactive properties using in vitro experimental model systems and utilization of enriched fish oil from FBP in pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals and feed sector](#)
- [Valorisation of polyphenols from by-products of marine plants in the cosmeceutical sector, and valorisation of carotenoids from shrimp, crab and other marine by-products](#)
- [Protocol and procedure for extraction carotenoid \(astaxanthin\) from marine by products](#)

- [Protocol and procedure for extraction of nitrogenic and proteic components, production of protein hydrolysates, from marine by products](#)
- [Circular Economy in the Fishery Value-Chain: Focus on Extraction and Valorisation](#)

4.4. Outcomes and Impact

The module contributed to the development of specialized professional profiles in marine biotechnology by:

- delivering applied technical knowledge on extraction and valorizations processes;
- strengthening career readiness for roles in R&D, sustainable innovation, and industrial bioeconomy sectors;
- providing a platform for interdisciplinary exchange, coaching, and idea development aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The training module successfully supported the BlueRev objective of promoting skilled job creation, innovation capacity, and the transition to circular marine-based economies.

4.5 UNIPA credit system

UNIPA will align to academic rules, releasing, upon participants' request, 1 ECTS per module (1 ECTS/8 hours of teaching).

5. EMU Training

As part of the BlueRev Project, the Estonian University of Life Sciences (EMU) developed a targeted training programme aimed at increasing small-scale actors in the blue bioeconomy and fostering the creation of skilled job opportunities. The programme aimed to:

- promote skilled job opportunities in rural and coastal areas;
- foster an entrepreneurial mindset in the bioeconomy;
- provide practical business development tools aligned with sustainability frameworks;
- strengthen the link between education, innovation, and territorial development.

5.1. Structure of the Programme

The module was developed in a way that all its topics could be combined into a full course (Sustainable innovation in blue bioeconomy for rural development), or each topic could be used for a standalone training event for students and SMEs.

5.2. Module 3: Training to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy and to increase skilled job opportunities

This module was divided into five thematic topics/sub-modules, addressing key areas for sustainable, inclusive, and innovation-driven growth in the blue bioeconomy. It combined lectures, group work, interactive exercises, BlueRev case studies, and business development tools to help participants from all disciplines systematically operationalize the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their ideas and start-ups, with a strong focus on rural and coastal contexts.

Link to the repository: [Module 3-EMU](#)

Topic 1: Blue bioeconomy: concepts, drivers, and Sustainable Development Goals

The module introduces the main concepts and definitions related to the blue bioeconomy, its drivers and trends, Sustainable Development Goals and the European Union Green Deal.

Key contents:

- Definition and evolution of the blue bioeconomy, its drivers, subsectors, and growth trends
- Main challenges and opportunities at regional and local level, especially in rural and coastal areas.

- Required resources (economic, social, natural) for sustainable development.
- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with focus on SDG 14.
- European Green Deal and its relevance to the blue economy.
- Principles of blue growth, circular economy, and green economy.
- Trends in employment, value added, trade, and consumption at EU and global levels.

Topic 2: Maritime planning and policy context for blue bioeconomy

This topic provided an overview of maritime spatial planning, related policy, international and regional strategies and agreements that direct blue bioeconomy development.

Key contents:

- Legislation, policy frameworks, and governance mechanisms regulating the blue bioeconomy at global, EU, and national levels.
- Marine Spatial Planning (MSP): objectives, tools, and implementation practices.
- Key institutions and actors: HELCOM, Natura 2000, and other relevant regulatory bodies.
- International and regional strategies and agreements shaping the blue bioeconomy.
- Planning and strategy principles for sustainable and inclusive marine resource management.
- Challenges related to legal complexity, multi-use of marine space, and cross-sectoral coordination.
- Integration of environmental, social, and economic considerations in blue bioeconomy planning.

Topic 3: Innovation in blue bioeconomy

This topic introduced different types of innovations in blue bioeconomy and business models and provided students/trainees with practical experience in developing a blue bioeconomy-related business idea using strategic business management tools such as the business model canvas to develop value creation thinking.

Key contents:

- Definition and classification of innovation types:
 - Product, process, marketing, organizational, and sustainable innovation in the blue bioeconomy context
- Innovation drivers and strategies for sustainable value creation
- The concept of sustainable innovation and its role in supporting circular and blue growth models

- Introduction to business model innovation:
 - Definition and strategic importance;
 - Overview of different types of Business Model Canvases (standard, sustainable, lean).
- Application of the Sustainable Business Model Canvas in business planning and idea development.

Topic 4: Collaboration models for sustainable blue bioeconomy in rural context

This topic introduced the main principles of collaboration and the role of private, public, and non-profit sectors in the blue bioeconomy development in rural areas, sustainable blue bioeconomy collaboration models for rural communities and best practices for collaboration and partnerships for innovations in blue bioeconomy.

Key contents:

- The role of partnerships, networks, and collaboration at global, regional, and local levels between private, public, and non-profit sectors in driving sustainable blue bioeconomy development.
- Design and plan sustainable collaboration models tailored to the needs of blue bioeconomy stakeholders, enterprises, and organisations in rural areas.
- Recognises the benefits of collaboration in the blue bioeconomy sector, including resource sharing, innovation, capacity building, and resilience.
- The importance of trust, social capital, and power relations in shaping effective and inclusive collaborative processes.

Topic 5: Social and governance innovations

This topic examined innovation ecosystems and introduced the social and governance innovation options in the blue bioeconomy context, and developed skills for creating a social innovation project supporting local communities.

Key contents :

- Ecosystems approach and definition of innovation ecosystems.
- Stakeholders, resources, and dynamics in rural blue bioeconomy innovation systems.
- Mapping of innovation ecosystems.
- Definition and principles of governance, collaborative and multilevel governance.
- Governance challenges and enablers in blue growth.
- Definition and types of governance innovation.
- Social innovation: definitions, theoretical models, conditions, and best practices.

Figure 4: Training organized by EMU

5.3. Outcomes and Impact

Each topic/sub-module was designed with clearly defined learning outcomes and aimed to develop key transversal skills such as critical thinking, teamwork, effective communication, and an entrepreneurial mindset. The programme supported the integration of sustainability into entrepreneurship, encouraging participants to engage actively with real-world challenges in the blue bioeconomy, particularly within rural and coastal contexts.

The training significantly strengthened the capacity of students, early-stage entrepreneurs, and SMEs to develop viable, sustainability-oriented business ideas aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Through hands-on activities and applied methodologies, participants acquired practical competencies in business development, innovation management, and governance models tailored to the blue bioeconomy.

The initiative also fostered cross-sectoral collaboration, stimulated entrepreneurship and job creation, and promoted inclusive, impact-driven innovation. Thanks to its modular and adaptable structure, the programme can be replicated in diverse regional contexts, offering long-term benefits for policy implementation, educational innovation, and sustainable local development strategies.

The training will continue to be used after the end of the project, as the course 'Sustainable Innovation in Blue Bioeconomy for Rural Development' will remain active and will be offered by EMU in upcoming academic years after the end of the project. The training materials are designed to be used both by Kuressaare College at the Estonian hub and in future trainings conducted by EMU.

5.4 EMU credit system

The full module (5 topics/sub-modules + final assessment) was 4 ECTS (104 hours, incl. face-to-face lectures and practical seminars in class, and independent work by the participants), as 1 ECTS = 26 hours, according to EMU regulation of Studies. Each topic/sub-module was 5.5 academic hours of in-class teaching.

6. APRE Training

The training programme aimed to empower small businesses by equipping them with the knowledge, tools, and practical examples needed for effective, transparent, and strategic communication with consumers. It was specifically designed for members of producer associations operating in the blue bioeconomy, including fishers, fish processors, and algae growers, collectors, and processors.

6.1. Structure of the Programme

The training consisted of a single module (Module 4) and was delivered through a series of four webinars. Each session focused on a key communication theme, building progressively to provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of communication practices tailored to small-scale operators in the bioeconomy. The structure was designed to foster capacity building in areas such as value proposition development, consumer engagement, and alignment with EU sustainability goals.

6.2. MODULE 4: Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy

Webinar 1: Introduction to the concepts of communication and innovation in the bioeconomy sector

This session explored the key concepts of communication and innovation, with a particular emphasis on the bioeconomy and the blue bioeconomy. It outlines the difference between greenwashing and transparent communication and provides an overview of the key elements of an effective communication strategy.

Link to the repository: [Introduction to the concepts of communication and innovation in the bioeconomy sector](#)

Webinar 2: How to write an effective communication plan

During this session, participants learned what a communication campaign is and what steps are needed to define an effective communication plan. The webinar provided practical examples of how to write different communication messages and the most appropriate communication styles based on the target audience, as well as examples of the best channels and tools to be used to maximise the campaign's impact.

Link to the repository: [How to write an effective communication plan](#)

Webinar 3: Communicating innovation: Examples from the BlueRev project

This webinar showcased real-life communication strategies adopted by small businesses involved in the BlueRev project in Italy, Estonia, and Denmark. Participants analysed how different regional actors addressed consumer awareness, integrated traditional and modern narratives, and promoted sustainability through innovative communication approaches.

Link to the repository: [Communicating innovation: examples from the BlueRev project](#)

Webinar 4: Barriers in the bioeconomy sector

This webinar explained what are the potential barriers for the implementation of bioeconomy initiatives, providing examples coming from a survey conducted within an EU-funded project. It analyses investment barriers, demand-side policy barriers, and regulatory barriers. It focuses on stakeholders' perception and acceptance barriers, through a specific example in the blue bioeconomy field.

Link to the repository: [Barriers in the bioeconomy sector](#)

Figure 5: Training organized by APRE

6.3. Outcome and Impact

The training programme improved participants' ability to communicate effectively and transparently with consumers, ensuring their messaging aligned with sustainability principles and EU policy goals. Key outcomes included increased awareness of communication strategies, an improved ability to develop bespoke communication plans, and stronger knowledge exchange across regions. The expected impact is greater

visibility and marketability of sustainable blue bioeconomy products, improved consumer engagement, and broader adoption of responsible communication practices among small-scale producers.

7. Online repository

The BlueRev training programme was delivered through two primary formats: online webinars and on-site or hybrid classroom lectures conducted at educational, research institutions, and SMEs. This dual delivery approach ensured both flexibility and inclusiveness, reaching a broad audience across regions and professional backgrounds.

To guarantee long-term accessibility and reference value, all training sessions were recorded. Where the quality of on-site recordings did not meet the required technical standards, sessions were re-recorded in a controlled environment to ensure optimal audio-visual clarity and educational effectiveness.

All recorded lessons and supporting materials are now available on the official BlueRev Training Support Tool, an online repository designed to host and disseminate the project's capacity-building outputs: <https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/>.

The platform serves as a centralised knowledge hub for stakeholders interested in advancing sustainable practices in the blue bioeconomy sector, including students, researchers, policymakers, and industry actors.

Below is an overview of the training content hosted on the platform:

Partner	UNIPA
Module 1	<u><i>Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy:</i></u> 1) Best practices for characterisation and selection of fish by-products (FBP) and co-products (FCP) from fishery, aquaculture and processing plant, to be applied at industrial level.
Link	https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/course/view.php?id=16
Target audience	Associations of producers (fishermen, fish processors, algae growers/collectors/processors).
Module 2	<u><i>Training/coaching programme to increase skilled job opportunities:</i></u> 1) Methods for extraction of bioactive compounds from FBP and FCP from pilot to industrial scale. 2) Extraction of Bioactive Compounds and Valorisation of Marine Resources.
Link	1) https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/course/view.php?id=13#section-1; 2) https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/course/view.php?id=13#section-2

Target audience	Master and PhD students in chemistry, biochemistry and marine biotechnology.
	Webinar associated with training
Webinar 1	Methods for extraction of bioactive compounds from fish by product and fish co products from pilot to industrial scale
Webinar 2	From conventional methods to green technologies and comparison of yield, quality and bioactivities of the fraction/compounds extracted
Webinar 3	Extraction of fish oils and enrichment in omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA)
Webinar 4	Evaluation of bioactive properties using in vitro experimental model systems and utilization of enriched fish oil from FBP in pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals and feed sector
Webinar 5	Valorisation of polyphenols from by-products of marine plants in the cosmeceutical sector, and valorisation of carotenoids from shrimp, crab and other marine by-products
Webinar 6	Protocol and procedure for extraction carotenoid (astaxanthin) from marine by products
Webinar 7	Protocol and procedure for extraction of nitrogenic and proteic components, production of protein hydrolysates, from marine by products
Webinar 8	Circular Economy in the Fishery Value-Chain: Focus on Extraction and Valorisation
Partner	EMU
Module 3	<u><i>Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy and to increase skilled job opportunities:</i></u> 1) Business development tools that students/employees in all disciplines can utilise to work systematically with operationalisation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals in their ideas and start-ups.
Link	https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/course/view.php?id=15
Target audience	Master and PhD students in agro-food technology, economy, bioeconomy and associations of producers (fishermen, fish processors, algae growers/collectors/processors).
Partner	APRE
Module 4	<u><i>Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy:</i></u> 1) Empowering the small business with the knowledge, tools and practical examples of how to effectively communicate when addressing consumers.
Link	https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/mod/data/view.php?id=54
Target audience	Associations of producers (fishermen, fish processors, algae growers/collectors/processors).

	<u>Introduction to the concepts of communication and innovation in the bioeconomy sector</u>
	<u>How to write an effective communication plan</u>
	<u>Communicating innovation: examples from the BlueRev project</u>
	<u>Barriers in the bioeconomy sector</u>

Table 1. BlueRev link to online material

8. References

8.1. Reference literature for UNIPA training

- Moran, S. B. 2021. Workforce development and leadership training for the new blue economy." In *Preparing a workforce for the new blue economy*, edited by L. Hotaling and R. W. Spinrad, 407–416. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-821431-2.00002-0>.
- Borriello, A., Calvo Santos, A., Codina Lopez, L., Curtale, R., Feyen, L., Gaborieau, N., Garaffa, R., Ghiani, M., Guillen, J., Mc Govern, L., Norman, A., Peralta Baptista, A., Petrucco, G., Pistocchi, A., Alonso Pleguezuelo, M., Quatrini, S. And TAPOGLOU, E., The EU blue economy report 2024, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/186064>, JRC138337.
- Messina CM, Manuguerra S, Arena R, Renda G, Ficano G, Randazzo M, Fricano S, Sadok S, Santulli A. (2021a). In Vitro Bioactivity of Astaxanthin and Peptides from Hydrolysates of Shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*) By-Products: From the Extraction Process to Biological Effect Evaluation, as Pilot Actions for the Strategy "From Waste to Profit." *Mar Drugs*; 19:216. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md19040216>.
- Messina, C.M., Arena R., Manuguerra, S., Renda, G., Laudicella, V.A., Ficano, G., Fazio, G., Barbera, L. La, Santulli, A., (2021b). Farmed Gilthead Sea Bream (*Sparus aurata*) by-Products Valorization: Viscera Oil ω -3 Enrichment by Short-Path Distillation and In Vitro Bioactivity Evaluation. *Marine. Drugs* 19: 160. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md19030160>
- Messina, C.M., Arena, R., Manuguerra, S., Pericot, Y., Curcuraci, E., Kerninon, F., Renda, G., Hellio, C., Santulli, A., 2021c. Antioxidant Bioactivity of Extracts from Beach Cast Leaves of *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile. *Mar. Drugs* 2021, Vol. 19, Page 560 19, 560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md19100560>
- Messina, C.M.; Arena, R.; Manuguerra, S.; La Barbera, L.; Curcuraci, E.; Renda, G.; Santulli, A. Valorization of Side Stream Products from Sea Cage Fattened Bluefin Tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*): Production and In Vitro Bioactivity Evaluation of Enriched ω -3 Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids. *Mar. Drugs* 2022, 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md20050309>
- Arena, R., Manuguerra, S., Curcuraci, E., Cusimano, M., Lo Monaco, D., Di Bella, C., Santulli, A., Messina, C.M., 2023. Fisheries and aquaculture by-products modulate growth, body composition, and omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acid content in black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae. *Front. Anim. Sci.* 4, 1204767. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fanim.2023.1204767>.
- Arena, R.; Renda, G.; Ottaviani Aalmo, G.; Debeaufort, F.; Maria Messina, C.; Santulli, A. Valorization of the Invasive Blue Crabs (*Callinectes sapidus*) in the Mediterranean: Nutritional Value, Bioactive Compounds and Sustainable By-Products Utilization. *Mar. Drugs* 2024, 22, 430. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md22090430>.

8.2. Reference literature for EMU training

Module 1

The Blue bioeconomy <https://youtu.be/WEp3fFleZc4?si=-NaBbB25cT7uJhUE> ;

BlueRev project <https://youtu.be/Uwv2uB9wFC0>

European Commission Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries. (2018). Blue bioeconomy - Situation report and perspectives, Publications Office of the European Union, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/053734>.

European Commission. (2019). Communication from the commission to the european parliament, the european council, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions the European Green Deal. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>

European Commission. (2021). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: On a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU – Transforming the EU's blue economy for a sustainable future (COM(2021) 240 final).

European Commission. (2023). The EU fish market: 2023 edition. European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products.

European Commission. (2024). The EU blue economy report 2024 (No. KL-AR-24-001-EN-N). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2771/186064>.

European Commission; Sijtsma, L., Guznajeva, T., Le Gallou, M., Eaton, D. et al. (2020). Blue Bioeconomy Forum - Roadmap for the blue bioeconomy, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/605949>.

Evans, L. S., Buchan, P. M., Fortnam, M., Honig, M., & Heaps, L. (2023). Putting coastal communities at the center of a sustainable blue economy: A review of risks, opportunities, and strategies. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2022.1032204>.

Louey, P. (2022). The blue economy's retreat from equity: A decade under global negotiation. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2022.999571>.

Naylor, R. L., Hardy, R. W., Buschmann, A. H., Bush, S. R., Cao, L., Klinger, D. H., Little, D. C., Lubchenco, J., Shumway, S. E., & Troell, M. (2021). A 20-year retrospective review of global aquaculture. *Nature*, 591(7851), 551–563. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03308-6>.

OECD. (2023). The benefits and costs of the blue economy at the territorial level. OECD Publishing.

Silver, J. J., Gray, N. J., Campbell, L. M., Fairbanks, L. W., & Gruby, R. L. (2015). Blue Economy and Competing Discourses in International Oceans Governance. *The Journal of*

Environment & Development, 24(2), 135–160.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1070496515580797>.

Spalding, M. J. (2016). The New Blue Economy: the Future of Sustainability. *Journal of Ocean and Coastal Economics*, 2 (2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15351/2373-8456.1052>.

United Nations. (2023). The Sustainable Development Goals report: Progress chart 2023. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs.

United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. United Nations. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>.

World Bank, United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2017). The Potential of the Blue Economy: Increasing Long-term Benefits of the Sustainable Use of Marine Resources for Small Island Developing States and Coastal Least Developed Countries. World Bank. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/a36b153d-0284-58b0-b7b3-35a26438f31b>.

Module 2

Angus, S. 2017. Modern seaweed harvesting and gathering in Scotland: the legal and ecological context. *Scott. Geogr. J.* 133 (2), 101–114.

Belinskij, A., Camarena G´omez, T., Kostamo, K., Lähteenmäki-Uutela, A., Piiparinen, J., & Spilling, K. 2021. Achieving blue growth and environmental objectives: legal regulation of novel blue biomass solutions in the Baltic Sea. GRASS Policy Brief 2.

Available online at: https://www.submariner-network.eu/images/grass/GRASS_PolicyBrief-2_ENG.pdf.

Camarena-Gómez, M.T., Lähteenmäki-Uutela, A., & Spilling, K. 2022. Macroalgae production in Northern Europe: Business and government perspectives on how to regulate a novel blue bioeconomy, *Aquaculture*, Volume 560, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738434>.

Domínguez-Tejo, E., Metternicht, G., Johnston, E., Hedge, L. 2016. Marine Spatial Planning advancing the Ecosystem-Based Approach to coastal zone management: A review. *Marine Policy*, Volume 72, 115-130, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2016.06.023>.

Estonia Government. 2019. Water Act. Available online at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/527122019007/consolide>.

Estonian Government. 2019. Estonian Maritime Spatial Plan. Draft Plan. Available online at: http://mereala.hendrikson.ee/dokumentid/Eskiis/Estonian_MSP_draft_plan_ENG.pdf.

European Commission. 2012. Blue Growth Opportunities for Marine and Maritime Sustainable Growth (COM (2012) 494 final).

European Commission. 2020. EU strategy for the Baltic Sea Region ACTION PLAN.

Commission staff working document, Brussels.

European Parliament and the Council. 2014. Directive 2014/89/EU, Brussels.

European Commission, Study on Blue growth, Maritime Policy and EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region, Brussels.
https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/system/files/Final%20Report%20Revision%206%20Dec%202013_NEW%20TEMPLATE.pdf.

Friess, B., & Marie Grémaud-Colombier. 2021. Policy outlook: Recent evolutions of maritime spatial planning in the European Union. *Marine Policy*, Volume 132, 103428.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.01.017>.

Schultz-Zehden, A., Weig, B., & Lukic, I. 2019. Maritime spatial planning and the EU's The blue growth policy: past, present and future perspectives, in: J. Zaucha, K. Gee(Eds.), *Maritime Spatial Planning, Past, Present, Future*, Palgrave, Cham, pp. 121–149.

UNEP, FAO, IMO, UNDP, IUCN, World Fish Center, GRID Arendal. 2012. Green Economy in a Blue World. UNEP/GRID-Arendal. <https://unctad.org/system/files/non-official-document/ted-ditc-05122016-cancun-GreenEconomy-Blue-unesp.pdf>.

Module 3

Ababouch, L., Nguyen, K. A. T., Castro de Souza, M., & Fernandez-Polanco, J. (2023). Value chains and market access for aquaculture products. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 54(2), 527–553. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12964>.

Bocken, N. M. P., Short, S. W., Rana, P., & Evans, S. (2013). A value mapping tool for sustainable business modelling. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 13(5), 482–497. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-06-2013-0078>.

Bocken, N. M. P., Schuit, C. S. C., & Kraaijenhagen, C. (2018). Experimenting with a circular business model: Lessons from eight cases. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 28, 79–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2018.02.001>.

Goffin, K., & Mitchell, R. (2017). *Innovation Management: Effective strategy and implementation*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

Naylor, R. L., Hardy, R. W., Buschmann, A. H., Bush, S. R., Cao, L., Klinger, D. H., Little, D. C., Lubchenco, J., Shumway, S. E., & Troell, M. (2021). A 20-year retrospective review of global aquaculture. *Nature*, 591(7851), 551–563. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03308-6>.

OECD (2018). *Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation. The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities*. Paris, Luxembourg: OECD Publishing, Eurostat.

Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business Model Generation. A Handbook for visionaries, game changers and challengers*. New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons.

Sustainable business model canvas (n.d). CASE Knowledge Alliance. https://www.case-ka.eu/wp/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/SustainableBusinessModelCanvas_highresolution.jpg.

Tidd, J., Bessant, J. (2018). *Managing Innovation: Integrating technological, market and organizational change* (6 tr.). Hoboken: Wiley.

Module 4

Armitage, D., Berkes, F., Dale, A., Kocho-Schellenberg, E., Patton, E. 2011. Co-management and the co-production of knowledge: Learning to adapt in Canada's Arctic. *Global Environmental Change*, Volume 21, Issue 3, 995-1004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.04.006>.

Fyall, A., Garrod, B., & Wang, Y. 2012. Destination collaboration: A critical review of theoretical approaches to a multi-dimensional phenomenon. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, Volume 1, Issues 1–2, 10-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2012.10.002>.

Guštin, Š., & Irma Potočnik Slavič. 2020. Conflicts as catalysts for change in rural areas. *Journal of Rural Studies*, Volume 78, 211-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2020.06.024>.

Lees, L., Karro, K., Barboza, F. R., Ideon, A., Kotta, J., Lepland, T., Roio, M., & Aps, R. 2023. Integrating maritime cultural heritage into maritime spatial planning in Estonia. *Marine Policy*, Volume 147, 105337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105337>.

Module 5

Fernández-Guerrero, D., Palazzolo-Henkes, R., Alba, M. F., Ramírez-Rodríguez, S., & Reig-Puig, L. (2022). Transnational Governance Frameworks for Sustainable Innovation: The Case Of The Blue Bioeconomy In The Mediterranean. *Economía Agraria y Recursos Naturales - Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 22(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.7201/earn.2022.02.04>

Massey, A., & Johnston-Miller, K. (2016). Governance: Public governance to social innovation? <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557314X14042230109592>

OECD (2024). *The Blue Economy in Cities and Regions*. OECD Urban Studies. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/the-blue-economy-in-cities-and-regions_bd929b7d-en.html.

Osburg, T., & Schmidpeter, R. (Eds.). (2013). *Social innovation: Solutions for a sustainable future*. Springer.

Soma, K., van den Burg, S. W. K., Hoefnagel, E. W. J., Stuver, M., & van der Heide, C. M. (2018). Social innovation – A future pathway for Blue growth? *Marine Policy*, 87, 363–370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.10.008>.

Wigboldus, S. (2016). Ten types of social innovation: A brief discussion paper. Wageningen Centre for Development Innovation.

8.3. Reference literature for APRE webinars

European Commission (2019) Entrepreneurship and Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes_en.

NNFCC Ltd (2019) Needs and challenges of companies in the bioeconomy in NW Europe, [needs-and-challenges_final_2019.pdf](#).

European Commission (2010) EUROPE 2020: A strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A52010DC2020>.

Paris, Bas & Michas et al. (2023). A Review of the Current Practices of Bioeconomy Education and Training in the EU. Sustainability. 15. 954. 10.3390/su15020954.

European Commission, The European Bioeconomy Strategy, https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy/bioeconomy-strategy_en.

9. Annex

[Webinar 1: Methods for extraction of bioactive compounds from fish by-products and fish co-products – from pilot to industrial scale.](#)

[Webinar 2: From conventional methods to green technologies: comparison of yield, quality and bioactivities of extracted fractions/compounds.](#)

[Webinar 3: Extraction of fish oils and enrichment in omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids \(PUFAs\).](#)

[Webinar 4: Evaluation of bioactive properties using in vitro models and application of enriched fish oils in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical and feed sectors.](#)

[Webinar 5: Valorisation of polyphenols from marine plant by-products in the cosmeceutical sector & carotenoids from shrimps, crabs and other marine by-products.](#)

[Webinar 6: Protocols and procedures for carotenoid \(astaxanthin\) extraction from marine by-products.](#)

[Webinar 7: Protocols and procedures for the extraction of nitrogenous and protein components: production of protein hydrolysates from marine by-products.](#)

[Webinar 8: Circular Economy in the Fishery Value-Chain: Focus on Extraction and Valorisation.](#)

Webinars released by APRE

 [Webinar 1 – Introduction to the Concepts of Communication and Innovation in the Bioeconomy.](#)

 [Webinar 2 – Creating an Effective Communication Plan.](#)

 [Webinar 3 – Practical Examples from the BlueRev Hubs.](#)

 [Webinar 4 – Challenges to Effective Communication in the Bioeconomy and the EU Effort.](#)

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